

Reactivity of 2'-Hydroxy-5'-Nitro-Chalkone Derivatives. Part 1

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Ethyl-2-(Substituted) phenyl-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro)phenyl- Δ^4 -cyclohexene-6-one-1-carboxylate derivatives are prepared from the corresponding 2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro-chalkones and ethyl acetoacetate. The esters on hydrolysis give the corresponding ketones which give 2 : 4-dinitro-phenylhydrazone derivatives.

The same chalkones give 1-phenyl-3-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro) phenyl-5-(substituted) phenyl-pyrazoline derivatives with phenylhydrazine hydrochloride.

Many workers¹ have studied the reactivity of chalkones with ethyl acetoacetate when ethyl- Δ^4 -cyclohexene-6-one-1-carboxylates are obtained which on alkaline hydrolysis give the corresponding ketones. Similar results are obtained in the present work with 2'-hydroxy-5'-nitrochalkones.

Similarly phenylhydrazine hydrochloride is known to give pyrazoline derivatives². The same type of compounds are obtained in the present work also, as shown by Knorr's pyrazoline reaction³ and Widman's test⁴.

With diethyl malonate, chalkones undergo Michael Addition⁵. In the present work, 2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro-chalkone only reacted, whilst other derivatives did not react.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl-2-(substituted) phenyl-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro) phenyl- Δ^4 -cyclohexene-6-one-1-carboxylate (I): The chalkone (1 g.) was mixed with ethyl alcohol (40 ml.) and metallic sodium (0.1 g.). Ethyl acetoacetate (1 ml.) and ethyl alcohol (20 ml.) were then added to it and the mixture boiled under reflux for about 6 hrs. When cold it was diluted and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product was crystallised from alcohol. The keto-esters are described in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Ethyl-2-(substituted)phenyl-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro)phenyl- Δ^4 -cyclohexene-6-one-1-carboxylate

Substituent	m.p. °C	M.F.	Found%	Reqd. %
R = H	190-91°	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ NO ₆	C, 66.3; H, 5.3; N, 3.8	C, 66.15; H, 4.98; N, 3.67
R = 2'-OCH ₃	179-80°	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ NO ₇	N, 3.62	N, 3.41
R = 4'-OCH ₃	203°	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ NO ₇	N, 3.60	N, 3.41
R = 3' : 4'.				
	197-8°	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ NO ₈	N, 3.32	N, 3.30
R = 3' : 4'- -di-OCH ₃	184-5°	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ NO ₈	N, 3.04	N, 3.17

2-(*Substituted*)phenyl-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro-)phenyl- Δ^4 -cyclohexene-6-one (II) : The above ester (1 g.) was treated with ethyl alcohol (40 ml.) and 5% solution of sodium hydroxide (20 ml.) and the mixture was heated for 6 hrs., cooled, diluted and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product was crystallised from alcohol. The compounds are described in Table 2 and characterised by 2 : 4-DNP derivatives which were crystallised from acetic acid and noted in Table 2.

1-Phenyl-3-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro)phenyl-5-(substituted) phenyl-pyrazoline (III)- To the aqueous solution (25 ml.) of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (2.5 g.) and crystalline sodium acetate (4.0 g.), chalcone (1 g.) in presence of alcohol (60 ml.) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. The solid obtained on diluting the cold mixture was crystallised from acetic acid. The compounds are described in Table 3.

To ethyl alcohol (40 ml.), 2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro-chalcone (1 g.) was added, followed by the addition of sodium metal (0.1 g.), diethyl malonate (2 ml.) and alcohol (20 ml.). The mixture was refluxed for 6 hrs. On cooling it was diluted and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 96°-7°.

TABLE 2

 2(Substituted)phenyl-4-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro)phenyl- Δ^4 -cyclohexene-6-*ond.* 2 : 4-DNP derivatives

Substituent	m.p. °C	M.F.	Found %	Reqd. %	m.p. °C	M.F.	Found %	Reqd. %
R = H	181-2°	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₄	C, 69.61; H, 5.10; N, 4.28	C, 69.90; H, 4.85; N, 4.53	177-8°	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₇	N, 14.20	N, 14.32
R = 2'-OCH ₃	200-01°	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₆	N, 3.80	N, 4.13	222-3°	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₈	N, 13.30	N, 13.49
R = 4'-OCH ₃	Shrinks at 197-8° and melts with decomposition at 212-3°.	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₆	N, 4.36	N, 4.13	222-3°	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₈	N, 13.40	N, 13.49
R = 3' : 4'-	229-30°	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₆	N, 4.31	N, 3.97	239-40°	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₈	N, 13.30	N, 13.13
R = 3' : 4'-di-OCH ₃	228-9°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ NO ₆	N, 4.02	N, 3.79	223-4°	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₉	N, 12.48	N, 12.75

TABLE 3

1-Phenyl-3-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro)phenyl-5-(Substituted)phenyl-pyrazoline

Substituent	m.p. °C	M.F.	Found%	Reqd. %
R = H	191-2	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	C, 70.40; H, 4.54; N, 11.90	C, 70.19; H, 4.74; N, 11.69
R = 2'-OCH ₃	173-4	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	N, 10.66	N, 10.80
R = 4'-OCH ₃	193-4	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	N, 11.00	N, 10.80
R = 3' : 4'- $\begin{array}{l} \text{—O} \\ \text{—O} \end{array} \rangle \text{CH}_2$	202-03	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	N, 10.76	N, 10.42
R = 3' : 4'- -di-OCH ₃	243-4	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₅	N, 9.70	N, 10.02

The compound is given the constitution as 1-(2'-hydroxy-5'-nitro)benzoyl-2-phenyl-2-diethylmalonyl-ethane (IV) viz.

Found : C, 61.57%; H, 5.33%; and N, 3.40%

C₂₂H₂₃NO₃ requires : C, 61.54%; H, 5.38% and N, 3.26%.

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